

A customizable secure DIY web application for accessing, sharing, and browsing aggregate experimental results and metadata.

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Abstract

Summary: A problem spanning across many research fields is that processed data and research results are often scattered, which makes data access, analysis, extraction, and team sharing more challenging. We have developed a platform for researchers to easily manage tabular data with features like browsing, bookmarking, and linking to external open knowledgebases. The source code, originally designed for genomics research, is customizable for use by other fields or data, providing a no- to low-cost DIY system for research teams.

Availability and Implementation: The source code of our DIY app is available on

<https://github.com/Carmona-MoraUCD/Human-Genomics-Browser>

It can be downloaded and run by anyone with a web browser, Python3 and Node.js on their machine. The web application is licensed under the MIT license.

Introduction

Preparing data for analysis involves retrieving processed data, research results and metadata. This is particularly applicable in writing processes (such as manuscripts, grant applications, or other documents). Typically, working data is in the form of individual tables (e.g., CSV files) summarizing results and metadata. Therefore, a common way to access it is through system browsing and retrieving different working sheets across several files. Securing the storage and sharing of this data is essential, as processed data and working results should maintain laboratory-specific identifiers to facilitate analyses. Scattered data poses a hindrance to efficient research. Our DIY web application allows users to upload datasets or processed results (CSV files), view and edit dataset information, link information to open databases, manage team users and permissions, and bookmark specific

information and datasets. It ensures data security with a permission system to prevent unauthorized access or changes. The UI is intuitive and allows easy access to extract information for other research processes (such as grant or publication writing).

REST API calls to the backend to update the UI based on user actions, including searching, editing the data, undoing edits, and deleting. The data architecture includes various objects, like users, datasets, data features, samples, etc. The information in the file is converted into objects and objects are linked using names. Displaying a table in the frontend based on the associated objects is handled by the web application. External APIs, like NCBI (Sayers *et al.* 2022), bioDBnet (Mudunuri *et al.* 2009), and Ensembl REST API (Yates *et al.* 2014; Martin *et al.* 2023), were used to obtain different feature information, in this case gene name, mRNA code sequence segments, assembly information, type of gene, etc. The frontend, backend, and external APIs together allow users to view, delete, edit, and upload processed data, results, and associated online information on a common platform. Besides providing easy access to research results, this web application can also enhance collaboration within a laboratory, while the code provides customizable options to tailor features to specific uses.

Architecture of Systems

The architecture tiers used to develop this application are discussed here and presented in Figure 1A.

Authentication: In order to use the web application, users must have an account to log into the system. Any user can create an account, but access to all pages is denied if the user's email is not registered in the system, as enabled by Auth0 (user management system) and MongoDB (email verification of registered user).

Uploading Dataset: The upload process starts upon the user submission of the file on the upload page. From the frontend, the application attempts to send the CSV file to the backend server. If it fails for any reason, it will notify the user through the browser. When the backend server receives the file, the parsing process begins. During parsing, the dataset undergoes cleanup such as omitting rows or columns with "NA" values. Then, the identifier words given by the user when uploading the data are used to identify the type of the dataset (i.e., feature – in this case, gene ID dataset or sample dataset). Finally, using pandas (a Python data manipulation library) (Data structures for statistical computing in python, McKinney, Proceedings of the 9th Python in Science Conference 2010; The pandas development team 2023), the server creates a list of data objects to be submitted to the MongoDB collection. The information of the dataset itself is submitted to the database. The ID is used to link the list and the dataset, allowing the removal of any feature or subject data when the dataset is deleted from the database.

Searching Data: The search function (for ID or dataset) sends the keyword to the backend server, which will perform a fuzzy search algorithm to display engine-like functionality, returning results with

a similar name to the keyword entered.

Tables in Dataset/Gene Pages: In each dataset or gene (feature) page, data can be previewed, which is fetched when the user accesses that page. The table edit functionality does not upload the edits every time the user makes one. Instead, all changes are sent to the backend collectively. Once updated, the information is fetched and the table preview will be edited on top of the original data, being stored for each dataset in a user-independent manner.

Bookmark: Bookmarking is possible at feature and dataset levels, and this information is stored in MongoDB for each user. After selecting the bookmark button, the page's ID is sent to the backend, triggering a request to MongoDB to store that ID information to the list in that specific user's information in MongoDB.

Additional APIs Used:

Although not primarily used, some external APIs were used to enrich the quality of the web application. NCBI DB (Sayers *et al.* 2022) was used to translate gene ID (feature ID) to its name. The API provided by GeneCards (Stelzer *et al.* 2016; Safran *et al.* 2021) creates an URL leading to a GeneCards page with search results for a specific gene. For visual enhancement, the web application displays colored segments of mRNA code. This was achieved using the bioDBnet API (Mudunuri *et al.* 2009) to convert the ENSEMBL gene ID (Yates *et al.* 2014; Martin *et al.* 2023) to the RefSeq mRNA Accession identifier, which was used to make an NCBI API call to fetch the mRNA code segment for a gene. Extra gene data (assembly information, type, and other identifiers/names) were fetched with the ENSEMBL API.

Functionalities

This Web Application enables the users to browse datasets, results, browse features (in this case gene data and gene information), search, edit datasets, and compare gene results (values) within a dataset (Figure 1B). Initially designed to browse and share genomics results and metadata, the web application can be customized for other projects (a detailed description of each existent functionality is in Supplementary Information).

Limitations

Although the current version has stable functionalities, the scalability of the web application could be refined to allow more requests, as currently the frontend server and the backend server are directly connected. Multiple backend servers and load balancing could be implemented to distribute the requests for improving the durability of the system.

Applications

Our work provides a new centralized processed/working data and metadata storage and sharing platform for research laboratories, offering an alternative to the common practice of using third-party storage services like OneDrive or Google Drive. This DIY customizable and secure web application facilitates the comparison of diverse data, results, and sample lists, by generating easily searchable and navigable pages, thereby eliminating the need to access multiple sources regularly. Additionally, users can add metadata and comments, while uploading data and results, which can assist for organization and analysis purposes.

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Supplementary Information

Detailed functionalities

The main functionalities are described using our gene browser web application as an example. The functionalities are divided into pages of the web application.

Home page: This is the initial view for users, visible before logging in. From this page, there are buttons through which users can reach the About Page (purpose of the web application) and Contact Page (relevant contact information).

Login/Signup (user): Users can create a new account or login using their account credentials. Anyone can create an account, but not every user can access all the resources. The login system was implemented since the purpose of the system is to share, store and analyze working data and results, which have project and internal identifiers in a working group. Additionally, access to viewing and manipulating data is restricted to authorized users.

Main Console Page: First landing page for the logged in user (previously registered by the admin, if not verified, the user is directed to a page that informs the need of admin verification). Users access all the functionality of the application with intuitive navigation, with buttons to search pages for genes or datasets. The page also displays the count of stored genes and datasets.

Upload: Admin-verified users can upload data (CSV format). Clicking the upload button transfers all data to the backend server, where necessary work, such as parsing the data, is done. Metadata can be entered at this point, such as description of dataset, link to a shared drive, etc. Some of the metadata is used for parsing, for example, in the sample gene database, sample or gene ID were used for the identification of the sample or gene columns during parsing; these values must be valid. There is error checking for this in the backend during parsing. Additionally, the dataset name is used for checking duplicated uploads by other users. Metadata can be edited if necessary.

Gene search: This page displays a search bar for typing keywords and can be accessed from the Main Console page. There is a drop-down selection that allows selecting the search fields, such as "Gene Name" or "Other Name" (alternative name for the Gene other than the Ensembl ID). The search results are fetched or refreshed after pressing the search button. This search is fuzzy, therefore there will be some ranking based on similarity. The results will have some basic information and a clickable link to the respective Gene Pages for the genes. There may be multiple entries for genes if multiple

datasets have the same gene. At the bottom of the Gene Search Page, there is a scrollable box with bookmarked genes using a card layout, with a clickable link and brief gene information.

Gene page: Each gene (or row in the CSV file) has its own page. A Gene Page displays information related to a specific gene with a tab layout. There are multiple tabs, and each contains a different group of information. Tabs include “Basic Info”, “Graph”, “Patients (or sample) Info”, and “Code Sequence”. The top of the page shows the name of the gene and a clickable bookmark icon, allowing users to bookmark the gene. Bookmarked genes show up in the Gene Search page’s scrollable box and in the user profile page. The “Basic Info” tab may pull information from an external source, if possible, but it will list information about the gene from the dataset, except gene IDs and gene values. In our case, we included a link to GeneCards (Stelzer *et al.* 2016; Safran *et al.* 2021) with search results related to this gene. The “Graph” tab shows plots of the gene values, offering two graph types. The “Patients (sample) Info” tab shows a table of samples and the gene values associated with the gene searched per sample. It is possible to filter the table based on different column values. The table or graphs are not editable, and they can be empty if the dataset has no samples.

Dataset search: This page displays a search bar for typing keywords, with search results fetched or refreshed after pressing the search button. The search is fuzzy, so there will be some ranking based on similarity. An external package with functions related to fuzzy search was used in the backend. The results will have basic information and a clickable link to the respective Dataset pages for the datasets. At the bottom of the Dataset Search Page, there is a scrollable box with bookmarked datasets. The bookmarked datasets use a card layout, with a clickable link and brief dataset information.

Dataset page: At the top, the Dataset Page has the title of the Dataset, date uploaded, and the bookmark icon. Tabs include “Basic Info”, “Genes Info”, and “Dataset Table”. The “Basic Info” tab has information like the number of genes, samples, etc. The “Genes Info” tab has a list of links corresponding to genes in this dataset. The list is in a single-column table, and it is possible to filter values. The “Dataset Table” tab has an editable table with all the samples and genes information. Users can view the last five edits for the dataset and undo any of them. It is possible to delete a dataset with a button click.

User page: This page allows users to check account/personal information, including their name, role, and bookmarked pages (mentioned in the next subsection). A logged in user can check their own page only.

Bookmark: Users can click the bookmark part on either the gene page or the dataset page and save the page for later use. Bookmarked pages are listed on the User Page (for the respective user) and can be accessed and unbookmarked from there.

User Management Page: This page can be accessed by users with the Admin role. It allows the Admin to add users by registering emails, delete users, and change their permissions. It also displays a history log of user permission changes to allow the Admin to check for any unexpected or odd modifications.

Legend to Figure 1

A. Architecture Overview. The main technology stacks of this web application are: React, Django, Auth0, MongoDB. React was used to implement the frontend and JavaScript to write the code. Django was used for the backend to create a connection between the frontend and the database. Any communication of data or processing of data is done using Django. MongoDB was used for the database, and NoSQL database was chosen for storage flexibility. Auth0 was used as an authentication system. **B. Application Path.** View of all the pages that exist in the sample web application and how users can move between those pages.